

COMPANY'S ACQUISITION AND ITS EMPLOYEES' SATISFACTION

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Abstract

Purpose – *The measure of the success or failure of mergers or acquisitions comes from numerical, economic, and commercial data. We want to figure out the impact of acquisitions on employees' satisfaction. We distinguish between senior-ranked and junior-ranked employees to give stakeholders better chances for success.*

Methodology/approach - *The main mechanism is a questionnaire. It was validated before being distributed among potential respondents. Using factor analysis, we determined three factors that express employees' satisfaction.*

Findings – *We found that generally, the three factors, namely Transparency and Communication, Involvement and Belonging, and Trust and Stability, cover several aspects of employees' feelings toward acquisitions or mergers. However, senior employees are significantly more satisfied than junior employees.*

Research limitations/implications – *The research emphasizes the need for junior employees' cooperation and involvement. It seems that senior employees were exposed to more details related to the acquisition.*

Practical implications – *The findings will help stakeholders pay more attention to junior-ranked employees and achieve better success while acquiring companies.*

Originality/value – *This is a phase in long-run research. Its value lies in quantitative measures of employees' attitudes and involvement in their organization's life.*

Key words: *acquisition, senior ranked employees, satisfaction.*

Introduction

Purchasing companies is a common and well-known process in various industries. Huge companies have acquired many companies worldwide. The measure of the success or failure of the purchase comes from numerical, economic, and commercial data. Its profitability and capacity for growth measure a company. The data can be impressive and promising but do not always indicate what is happening in society from a personal point of view.

The employees, the engine for the company's success or failure, are the human capital, and the degree of success depends on them. The employees who make up the company belong to all ranks, from the student-hourly worker to the senior manager. Everyone is responsible in one way or another for the company's success. Therefore, space must be made for every employee and harnessed for the company's success. Now, with the company's purchase, the company is going through upheavals both in terms of organizational culture and the lack of acknowledgments and transparency shown to the employees.

When you enter this process, you build an orderly plan regarding finances, profits, knowledge, information, markets, customers, etc., but no company builds a transition and "soft landing" plan for employees. This arose from the need to check the satisfaction of employees in companies that had undergone acquisition.

The research question is to what extent, if any, there is a difference between senior-ranked employees and junior-ranked employees regarding the company's purchase.

Literature Review

The literature survey is comprehensive and in-depth and includes many topics that create an overall picture. First shown the need and reasons for purchases and how the purchase is affected by the process of crossing the innovation threshold through purchases (Cefis and Marsili, 2015)

Today, companies acquire new companies to merge and bridge the gap between their current position and their future performance in terms of innovation and performance (Nathan, 2014).

All of these are examined using models for the impact of purchases on procurement, which we will expand on in the literature survey.

The main topic presented in the literature survey is the management of human resources as a necessary factor for the success of the purchase. When considering the success of a purchase, one of the influencing factors is human capital (Sinkovics et al. 2011). The studies show that the thorough management of human resources and their integration are necessary for the success of the process. Part of the sharing is reflected in the personal communication in the organization.

It is known that the purchase process is challenging, and sometimes, secrecy must first be maintained in order to avoid harming the negotiations. However, the issue of confidentiality is also an obstacle and a problem of lack of transparency with the employees. Hence, even in the stages of preparing the plan for the purchase, emphasis must be placed on communication and determining what information will be passed on to the employees and how it will be possible to reflect the process to them. This is one of the main characteristics of proper leadership among the organization and the management.

Later on, the issue of the effect on employment and workers' wages is also reflected. Studies show that there is a negative effect on the scope of the employed—a trend of constant decline—but at the same time a positive effect on wages. All studies show that there was an increase in workers' wages. In addition, it seems that purchases are a lever for occupational efficiency among the employees (Schuler, and Jackson, (2017).

The subject of the new organizational culture is also essential and central. The theoretical and research literature discusses the role of organizational culture in mergers and acquisitions and indicates that cultural differences can create major obstacles to achieving integration benefits. It is assumed that cross-border acquisitions perform better in the long term if the buyer and the target come from countries that are not culturally distinct.

The issue of cultural differences is especially reflected in global acquisition processes, in which the purchasing company and the acquired company come from different countries with great geographical distances.

The influence of the human aspect on the results of purchases. The research shows that complete transparency and frequent and enthusiastic communication about the change may reduce the employee's uncertainty during the change. The survey is comprehensive and

touches on several points, the main subject of which is the employees (Katsuyuki and Takuji, 2012).

Emotions play a significant role in the success of the purchase; these emotions affect the outcome variables. The initial assumptions of management are a significant factor in the merger process; Stimulation and push from management can affect the individual. Also, communication, the conduct of the managers, and the transparency and reliability of the information passed on to the employee will affect his feelings and, hence, his attitude and behaviour in the merger process (Philip and Finbar, 2002).

Methodology

The study population consists of students, production workers, office workers, managers, and senior managers who work in Israeli companies that have been acquired in recent years.

The research is quantitative, and questionnaires were used. The questionnaire was drafted after conducting the literature survey to be sufficient and cover all the topics and points with satisfaction that we must conclude. The purpose of examining the questionnaire is to check the relevance of the questions included in the questionnaire (validity) and the degree of clarity of the questions (reliability).

Both tests were done by judges using methods of apparent validity and inter-judge reliability. In addition, this examination helped us ensure that the questionnaire included all aspects relevant to the research topic. About 194 employees filled out the questionnaire that was distributed to the companies. The questionnaire was distributed in a computerized form to the employees' email and was also given manually to employees whose work does not require a personal computer.

The sampling methods used are non-probability sampling methods: manual delivery to selected employees among the production workers and workers and students. These employees volunteered to fill out the questionnaire. In addition, a convenience sample was used: sending the questionnaire by email to office workers and management personnel.

The questionnaire results were analysed in two parts: the first part is descriptive statistics, which describes the participants filling out the questionnaires in the various demographic segments using averages, standard deviations, minimum and maximum values, and more. The second part is inferential statistics, which describes the testing of research hypotheses using correlation and regression tests.

Employee satisfaction consists of several parameters, including transparency, communication, involvement, belonging, trust, and stability.

We defined three factors regarding employee satisfaction. 1) Transparency and Communication, 2) Involvement and belonging, and 3) Trust and Stability.

Findings

First, we presented the findings for the junior level about the three categories that make up the satisfaction.

First Category - transparency and communication

The average level of satisfaction regarding transparency and communication is 2.9; the employees feel that the company has a moderate degree of openness and communication.

Second Category - involvement and belonging

The satisfaction average regarding involvement and belonging stands at 3.1; that is, the employees feel that there is a moderate degree of involvement and belonging in the company.

Third Category - trust and stability

The satisfaction average regarding trust and stability is 2.97; the employees feel that trust and stability exist in the company to a moderate degree.

Second, we presented the findings for the senior level about the three categories that make up the satisfaction.

First Category - transparency and communication

The average level of satisfaction regarding transparency and communication is 3.6; the senior ranked employees feel that the company has a moderate degree of openness and communication.

Second Category - involvement and belonging

The satisfaction average regarding involvement and belonging stands at 3.5; that is, the senior employees feel that there is a moderate degree of involvement and belonging in the company.

Third Category - trust and stability

The satisfaction average regarding trust and stability is 3.3; the employees feel that trust and stability exist in the company to a moderate degree.

When all the junior-level results are collected, the findings for the junior level can be presented. With reference to the research hypotheses, one can see substantiation in the above findings—there is a gap in the participation of the employees and in treating them as human capital. Management and human resources do not emphasize the employee as a person.

According to the research findings, weighing all the results and the average of the three research categories discussing transparency, communication, involvement, belonging, trust, and a sense of stability, we concluded that people at the junior level feel only moderately satisfied with the organization. This indicates a lack of communication and transparency in the organization; the respondents do not feel safe enough, which can harm their loyalty in the workplace and create a lack of motivation that can directly harm their productivity and leakage of knowledge and workforce from the organization to the outside.

Discussion and conclusions

Comprehensive analysis of junior and senior level

In the study we surveyed a population of 194 respondents.

35% of the senior level respondents and about 65% of the junior level respondents.

First category - transparency and communication

For the junior level, the average satisfaction is 2.91, while the average satisfaction in the senior level is 3.58

The junior level employees feel transparency and communication to a moderate degree only compared to the senior level who feel transparency and communication to a great extent.

It can be understood that there is a difference in the sense of transparency and communication between the different levels, the senior level feels a different sense of security than the junior level.

Second category - involvement and belonging

For the junior level, the average satisfaction is 3.1, while the average satisfaction in the senior level is 3.54

The junior level employees feel involvement and belonging to only a moderate degree compared to the senior level who felt involvement and belonging in the organization to a large extent.

It can be understood that there is a difference in the feeling of involvement and belonging between the different levels, the senior level feels a different sense of security than the junior level.

Third category - trust and stability

For the junior level, the average satisfaction is 2.9, while the average satisfaction in the senior level is 3.32

Both ranks trust the company and feel only moderately stable.

In order to reduce the gaps between the ranks and harness all the company's employees to the company's success and progress, the employees must be strengthened and empowered, consolidated, explained and shared in the entire purchasing process. To impart a sense of security and stability in ways of complete transparency, providing information and general involvement. It must be remembered and internalized that employees who are satisfied with their workplace bring the company to many economic and business achievements and successes. Employees should be seen as human capital.

We recommend creating meetings in which management allows the employees to express their feelings and explain their positions while answering the employees' points to create trust, openness, and a feeling that there is someone to turn to and that there will be an appropriate response.

When employees feel a sense of security and stability in the workplace, their performance will improve accordingly.

Later, the research results for the senior level were presented about the three families that make up the satisfaction.

First Category - transparency and communication

The satisfaction average regarding transparency and communication is 3.58; that is, the employees feel that there is a great deal of transparency and communication in the company.

It was found that the average results for the background variables—gender, marital status, and age—were the same.

In addition, it was found that the background variables of seniority and education differ in examining the issue of transparency and communication.

The difference is reflected between employees with up to two years' seniority in the workplace and the rest of the employees. Those with low seniority feel that there is only a small amount of transparency and communication, with an average satisfaction of 2.2, while the rest of the employees feel that there is transparency and communication in the organization to a large extent.

It is possible that the difference in satisfaction stems from the gap in years of seniority at the workplace. In addition, the employees started their work in the existing situation after the purchase without knowing and feeling the changes that occurred before and after the purchase.

Also, there is another difference between those with a bachelor's degree and the rest with an average satisfaction of 3.04. Those with a bachelor's degree feel moderate transparency and communication in the company. In contrast, the rest of the research population thinks that there is a sense of openness and communication in the organization to a large extent.

Second Category - involvement and belonging

The satisfaction average regarding involvement and belonging stands at 3.54; the employees feel that there is a moderate degree of involvement and belonging in the company.

It was found that the average results for the background variables—sex, seniority, marital status, and age—were the same.

In addition, it was found that there is a difference in examining the issue of trust and stability in the background variable - education.

The significant difference is reflected between those with a bachelor's degree in average satisfaction of 2.8 and the rest of the sample population. According to the findings, those with a bachelor's degree feel that there is a moderate degree of trust and stability in the company, while the rest of the population feels that there is a large degree of trust and stability in the organization.

In order to reduce the gaps between the ranks and harness all the company's employees to the company's success and progress, the employees must be strengthened and empowered, consolidated, explained and shared in the entire purchasing process. To impart a sense of security and stability in ways of complete transparency, providing information and general involvement. It must be remembered and internalized that employees who are satisfied with their workplace bring the company to many economic and business achievements and successes. Employees should be seen as human capital.

Referring to the research questions and hypotheses, it was found that there is a gap between the ranks in the degree of satisfaction of the employees, and there is also a general feeling of a lack of transparency and communication when it comes to the issue of purchasing. It seems that there is no emphasis on human capital and the research confirmed and validated the issue.

Following the study, several points and ideas for further research emerged such as: there is a lack of management tools and a management tool adapted to the human resources in the organization must be built.

The recommendations for further research are based on the research we carried out, and are adapted to students specializing in the field of human resources. The tool will be able to be used by many companies and will be a complementary study to the gap and deficiencies identified in our studies.

Another recommendation is to divide the research population into engineers, marketing people, human resources people, R&D workers and check the degree of employee satisfaction according to the nature of their work.

Notes

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